

The Toils of AIS: A Case Study in Application Protocol Design And Analysis

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Introduction

The authors have written several decoders and codecs for the rather complex AIS protocol used by marine safety and navigation systems. Based on this experience, we put forward some lessons learned and design principles that we think should be heeded in the extension of AIS and the design of future application protocols. We also offer pragmatic advice to those implementing decoders for AIS and similar application protocols.

Overview of AIS

The Marine Automatic Identification System (AIS) is a software, hardware, and radio coding protocol that allows ships to broadcast navigational and other status information for use in collision avoidance, navigation, and traffic management. Early design work on AIS was done primarily by Sweden; the International Association of Lighthouse Authorities (IALA) proposed the concept to the International Maritime Organization (IMO) in 1995 [[IALA2004](#)]. The core AIS standard is now maintained by the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) in association with IMO [[ITU1374](#)].

Both the design of AIS and the process by which it evolved are representative of a large class of application protocols in the real world, especially those concerned with geolocation and geographic information systems. A marked feature of AIS, however, is that due to the hazards of operation at sea, the information it handles can be immediately life-critical. This gives software defects in decoders a special significance and raises the stakes in our design analysis.

The physical layer of AIS uses a self organizing (SO) variant of Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA) packet radio scheme to avoid collisions among AIS transmitters serving either of two operating frequencies [[LANS1996](#)]. For the analysis in this paper, the physical layer can be largely ignored and AIS viewed as a mechanism for passing binary datagrams in either an addressed or broadcast mode. For AIS purposes an "address" is a Maritime Mobile Service Identity (MMSI), a 9-digit numeric tag associated with a ship or shore station.

The binary datagrams have a fixed header containing a dispatch field (the type) followed by information whose formatting varies by type in complex ways. Payload information is encoded mainly as packed numeric bit fields of lengths varying from 1 to 30 bits; these may be interpreted as boolean flags, unsigned or signed two's-complement big-endian integers, indices into controlled vocabularies, or (implicitly, via scaling formulas) as fixed-point real numbers. Some messages have longer regions that are interpreted as character strings or treated as opaque binary blobs to be passed to from or to helper applications.

Typical data items to be extracted from AIS bit fields include latitudes, longitudes, vessel course and speed, capabilities of the transmitting vessel or station, and weather or safety conditions. Some message fields are passed solely for the AIS system's own housekeeping functions.

In practice, software engineers are unlikely to encounter AIS datagrams in raw binary form. AIS receivers commonly make them available over RS422, RS232 and USB ports in an ASCII-armored byte-stream form called AIVDM/AIVDO, a profile or variant of the NMEA format commonly used in shipboard navigation and control systems.

The design of AIS is optimized to make efficient use of scarce radio bandwidth. In this it resembles a great many application protocols which tight-pack every bit - either out of rational economy or (more commonly) because the designer's mental habits were formed in a time when bandwidth was far more expensive than it is today.

Raymond maintains a programmer's-eye view of the details of AIS/AIVDM/AIVDO in [\[RAYMOND1\]](#). Since that document is available from any browser, we choose not to burden this paper with duplicative details about datagram formats (but see the layout of the Common Navigation Block in the next section for a representative example, the payload of the three most common message types). We will refer to [\[RAYMOND1\]](#) frequently, and readers are assumed to be familiar with it before proceeding.

Complexity kills

It is hardly news that software defect rates rise with the complexity of the software. Software bugs frequently arise from unplanned interactions between different parts of a codebase. It follows that defect rates scale roughly as the square of codebase size. It is well known [\[MMM\]](#) that bugs tend to cluster at the interfaces between code written by different people; thus, defects also rise as the square of the number of coders on a project.

In life-critical systems such as AIS, software defects can kill people. Software complexity should therefore be viewed as an actual danger, a cause of avoidable deaths. Simplicity saves lives.

The benefits of software simplicity in non-life-critical systems, while less dramatic, are no less real. Defects incur downstream problems and maintenance costs; thus, software complexity should be viewed as a burden that does not end when the project ships, but which continues to incur costs over the entire service life of the software.

Complex application protocols require complex software to interpret them. Thus, application protocol complexity entails software complexity, which entails quadratically rising defect rates, which in life-critical systems implies avoidable deaths.

Accordingly, a central problem with AIS - and many other application protocols resembling it - is that it is exceedingly complex.

The problem is well indicated by the bulk of the base specification, [\[ITU1371\]](#). In the current Version 4 there are 27 message types with lengths varying from 72 to 1008 bits, described by 142 pages of dense standardsese. It is supplemented by two International Marine Organization circulars ([\[IMO236\]](#) and [\[IMO289\]](#)) defining 24 additional message subtypes in 78 additional pages of standardsese. The AIVDM/AIVDO ASCII packet format is described in yet another standard, [\[IEC-PAS\]](#). When taking into account the sub messages, the specifications allow for more than 262K message types.

There is a common paraphrase of a quote by Albert Einstein that advises us to "Make everything as simple as possible, but not simpler." Some part of AIS's complexity is essential to its function. For example, any application protocol that conveys numeric data has to have rules about how it is represented in the bits. Other parts of its complexity are accidental, simply a result of unfortunate design decisions.

The most prevalent cause of bad protocol-design decisions is not individual incompetence, but rather various sorts of cultural blindness affecting the design process. Experienced software engineers learn to recognize - and dread - the signs of an application protocol designed by domain specialists who do not understand how to avoid accidental complexity, or gravely underweight its costs.

We will anatomize in detail the accidental complexity of AIS. In so doing, we intend to illustrate by inversion how application-protocol designers can avoid costly and dangerous mistakes.

How complexity rises

Analyzing datagrams in a protocol like AIS is formally similar to parsing a context-free grammar (CFG). The goal, in both cases, is to digest a serial stream of incoming bits from an external source into an internal representation that uses the native data formats of the interpreting computer. This internal representation may then be used in any number of ways (e.g. visualization, report generation, and interpretation as a command sequence).

Parsing techniques for CFGs found in textual formats such as computer languages and document markups are a much-studied area of computer science, well-described in classics such as [\[ASU\]](#). Though it is less practiced, application of these same techniques to binary datagrams and streams remains valid for practical purposes and for estimations of algorithmic complexity. Tools such as [\[ASN.1\]](#) describe binary byte-stream protocols in this style. What specifically concerns us in this paper is to understand how to hold the complexity of the parsing stage to a minimum.

A CFG's complexity (and the complexity of associated parsers) is proportional to the number of productions (parsing rules) required to describe it. The analog of a terminal symbol in the grammar is a bitfield length and type, where *type* in this context includes not just numeric kind but associated interpretive data like offsets, scaling constants, and controlled-vocabulary lists.

Further, complexity in CFGs tends to have a Pareto's-law-like distribution: small irregularities and exception cases in some 20% of the language produces large ripple effects in the difficulty of parsing the other 80%. Accordingly, another class of problem to look out for is exception cases to general rules.

With this model in mind, let us tour the AIS message types in sequence, as an implementer generally would, looking at the specific ways they add complexity to the implied CFG. For the moment, ignore the many issues about the inventory of terminal symbols (bitfield types and interpretations), just as we would normally ignore most lexical issues in estimating the parse complexity of a conventional textual CFG. The boundaries among terminal symbol types are disputable, and the counts we give below should be considered approximations for scale-estimation purposes.

Types 1 through 4: Fixed-length felicity

Begin by considering the first three AIS message types described in Table 45 of [\[ITU1371\]-4](#), grouped as "Position Report Class A", but ignore the trailing communication state. These differ only in type number and its interpretation, which is outside the parser's scope. They can therefore be regarded as one production in the grammar; in [\[RAYMOND1\]](#) it is called the Common Navigation Block (CNB).

Field	Len	Description	Type	Units and Meaning
0-5	6	Message Type	unsigned int	Constant: 1-3
6-7	2	Repeat Indicator	unsigned int	Message repeat count
8-37	30	MMSI	unsigned int	9 decimal digits

38-41	4	Navigation Status	enumerated	Moored, under way, etc.
42-49	8	Rate of Turn (ROT)	signed real	Degrees per minute
50-59	10	Speed Over Ground (SOG)	unsigned real	Meters per second
60-60	1	Position Accuracy	boolean	High-accuracy flag
61-88	28	Longitude	signed real	Minutes/10000
89-115	27	Latitude	signed real	Minutes/10000
116-127	12	Course Over Ground (COG)	unsigned real	Degrees from true north.
128-136	9	True Heading (HDG)	unsigned int	Degrees from true north.
137-142	6	Time Stamp	unsigned int	Second of UTC timestamp

143-144	2	Maneuver Indicator	enumerated	
145-147	3	Spare		Not used
148-148	1	RAIM flag	boolean	Receiver Autonomous Integrity Monitoring enabled and valid?
149-167	19	Radio status	variable structure	Status bits for cell radio

The CNB is fixed-length and has a fixed sequence of sixteen fields, spanning sixteen types, in 160 bits. It is thus dead-simple to parse. In C, one could easily decode the bits with no moving parts (formally, no control logic) by reading the entire datagram into memory (where it would take up a grand total of 20 bytes) and casting it into a structure full of bit fields (which, on a little-endian machine, would alas have to be flipped end-to-end).

From a reliability-engineering point of view, this is a best case scenario and a very promising start. However, see later discussion of field-specification issues for some troubling problems with individual fields in these three messages

Message type 4, "Base Station Report", is also fixed-length and fixed-sequence and can thus also be parsed with no moving parts. While it introduces nine new field types (including our first controlled vocabulary index) the increase in overall complexity is low.

Type 5: The six-bit blunder

With message type 5, "Ship static and voyage related data", complexity begins to rise. This type is still fixed-length with a fixed sequence of 21 fields, and introduces only five new types. Three of the Type 5 fields (Call Sign, Vessel Name, and Destination) are character-string data in a 64-bit subset of ASCII packed as 6-bit nybbles. Unfortunately, it is dramatically more complex to decode this oddly packed strings than the fixed-length numerics and flag bits we've been dealing with so far.

This is a paradigm for the sort of fixation on tightest-possible bit packing that makes software engineers blanch. Before this 6-bit data can be used, it needs to be unpacked into conventional 8-bit bytes. Not only have we lost the simplicity of being able to decode the message just by statically slicing it into fixed-length bitfields, the moving parts of the unpacking logic turn out to be easy to get wrong in ways that are tricky to diagnose. This is not merely theoretical criticism; Raymond found a longstanding bug in a preexisting AIS decoder ([\[GNU-AIS\]](#)) exactly here.

The fact that these strings aren't coded in byte-aligned 8-bit ASCII or UTF-8 is the first serious blob of accidental complexity in AIS. The 6-bit data occupies 262 bits of a 424-bit message format in 47 nybbles. The cost of 8-bit-ASCII would have been a 22% increase in message length, but going from 2 to 2.34 slots (requiring 3 slots to transmit). At the type 5 transmission interval and data rates prescribed in [\[ITU1371\]](#) this implies an additional transmission cost of 0.004% of the VHF data link available slots. For 100 ships in an AIS cell, the overall cost would be 0.37% of the available slots.

[\[ITU1374\]](#)-4 alludes to an international process underway of allocating two more AIS channels. These channels may be at much higher frequencies than VHF and afford much more than 9600bps bandwidth as they will be optimized for satellite reception.

Thus, the designers of AIS incurred a substantial increase in the complexity of decoders in order to save the equivalent of two tenths of one percent of a duty cycle. This is our first "Never, **ever** do this!" It is a blunder that could only arise from being fixated on hardware-layer economy while ignoring the defect-rate implications and testing costs for the software layer.

Furthermore, over time bandwidth tends to become less expensive while defect- and maintenance-related costs in software tend to remain steady or rising. Thus, the choice that was a bad tradeoff in 1998 when [\[ITU1371\]](#) first issued looks worse today, ten years later. It will look still worse ten years from now.

Type 6 and 8: Dynamic allocation is not your friend

With type 6, "Addressed binary message", two more forms of complexity are introduced. One is minor and arguably essential; the other is major and completely accidental. We'll consider types 6 and 8 together, as type 8 is structured in essentially the same way as 6 except for omitting destination information and housekeeping information for point-to-point transmission; it is instead designed for broadcast messages.

The minor increment is that message types 6 and 8 have a bit length that is variable rather than fixed. These messages are a wrapper around a binary payload of up to 920 (type 6) or 952 (type 8) bits, which is the last field.

In the specific context of AIS, this sort of variable-length payload poses no special difficulty. Because the message length tops out at 1008 bits = 126 bytes, it is feasible to unpack it in a static buffer of maximum size and ignore the tiny amount of waste space.

This is not in general true of application protocols with bulkier payloads, for which handling variable-length datagrams often requires dynamic memory allocation. And, in languages like C or C [without automatic garbage collection, dynamic-memory allocation is a notorious source of](#)

defects. Indeed, many audits of large C/C codebases have found it to be the single worst source of data corruption, security problems, and crash bugs. On the other hand, languages which avoid this problem through support of variable-extent data structures and garbage collection are often too bulky to fit in embedded deployments or too subject to GC-related stalls to be suitable for real-time use.

Application-protocol designers should therefore think twice before incurring this complexity as a side effect of their designs. But at least this is often essential complexity, a kind that is entailed in the application requirements.

Type 6 and 8 continued: Overextension is your enemy

Unfortunately, interpretation of types 6 and 8 introduces another kind of complexity that is completely accidental and (in the AIS context) far worse. Interpretation of the binary payload is both variable and ambiguous.

Early versions of the base AIS specification reserved 16 bits before the actual payload as an "application identifier". This was subdivided into a 10-bit "designated area code" (DAC) and a six-bit "functional identifier" (FID). The intention for types 6 and 8 at that time appears to have been as a conduit for private and encrypted data. The world's Coast Guards and Navies are known to use AIS this way ("blue force AIS" or E-AIS). There was no complexity increment to general-purpose decoders in this scheme; any extra burden fell on private applications generating and interpreting those payloads.

All this changed when the ITU delegated control of message 6 and 8 layouts to regional authorities by DAC. These messages then became an extension mechanism that controlling authorities for a designated area could use to define their own payload formats without extending or revising the base standard. The St. Lawrence Seaway (DACs 366 and 316) and the International Maritime Authority (DAC 1) promptly did so.

While this may have been bureaucratically convenient, the result was a confusing proliferation of public message subtypes, some pushed through without adequate review (for example, [\[IMO236\]](#) contains obvious signs of drafting errors in the FID=12 "Number of persons on board" specification). As of early 2011 there are 24 such subtypes in the international DAC alone, requiring approximately as much additional complexity as the entirety of [\[ITU1371\]](#).

If the result had been to preserve fixed-field simplicity for each message type while merely bloating the overall volume of decoders, the implications for complexity and defect loads would have been worrying but readily manageable. But the damage did not end there.

Before, the only field of an AIS message that could act as a dispatch to different bitfield sequences was the message-type field in the header. Under the new rules, the payload part in these so-called "functional" messages of type 6 and 8 could have any number of different bitfield sequences depending on the joint value of two more dispatch fields, DAC and FID.

In one particularly egregious example of misdesign, the IMO289 "Weather Observation From Ship" (DAC = 1, FID = 21) sprouted two variants and a **fourth** dispatch field, a flag at bit offset 56 ("Type of weather report")!

The increment to the minimum complexity of decoders was quite large, larger in fact than the jump from the packed-sixbit blunder. But the damage didn't even end there, as ships under the jurisdiction of some Designated Areas began sending IMO extension messages with IMO236 or IMO289 FIDs paired with local DACs other than 1. It became impossible to reliably distinguish IMO special messages from poorly-documented local conventions without a growing exception list.

The confusion had become complete. And this is before we even enter into the additional complexity of the actual special-message payloads, which we shall not attempt to fully describe here. Sufficiently masochistic readers can find the details in [\[RAYMOND1\]](#) and [\[IMO289\]](#).

All this complexity appears, quite understandably, to have stalled out adoption of the IMO special-message types. In searches of data from [\[AISHUB\]](#) and [\[NAIS\]](#), which pools AIS reports for over 150 AIS receivers scattered all over the world, we have yet to unambiguously detect any of the 19 messages described in IMO289 aside from these three: 8:1:11 (Met/Hydro deprecated), 8:1:26 (Environmental), 8:1:22 (Area Notice - broadcast) in two years of trying (the later two are from USCG test bed receivers in Tampa, FL and Provincetown, MA). It is highly doubtful that there is enough volume to motivate vendors of AIS receivers to undertake the expensive task of upgrading their firmware and display applications.

All of this complexity - and the increased defect rate it implies - appears to have been self-defeating, loaded on to little or no purpose and requiring decoder implementations to include essentially useless code in order to check off standards-conformance boxes.

Had the ITU/IMO stuck with its single original extension mechanism (the type field in the header) and added only new message types with a fixed bitfield sequence, it seems far more likely that these messages would have achieved useful deployment.

Types 6 and 8: Point defects

Attempting to describe all the design defects in the IMO extension messages would certainly exhaust the reader's patience and possibly endanger his or her sanity. But some of the simpler ones deserve examination because they can be used to illustrate sound design principles by negative example.

Some of the type 6 and 8 extension messages feature trailing variable-length arrays of record structures. One of the simpler examples is Route Information; the addressed and broadcast versions have a fixed-length header followed by 1 to 16 latitude/longitude pairs representing waypoints. Another is Tidal Window, with 1 to 3 more complex trailing structures representing tidal-current conditions.

In general, when AIS messages have variable-length trailing sections the actual length of the trailer is implicit from the message's overall bit length. Tidal Window, in particular, is organized this way, But Route Information is an exception; the last field in the fixed-length part is a waypoint count.

There are two problems with this. First, the existence of that waypoint count field violates the Single Point of Truth principle. It is redundant with the message bit-length, and may even

contradict it if the message generator has a bug. All the complexity and defects produced by having to cope with this possibility are completely accidental and unnecessary.

The second problem is that this one exception exactly doubles the code complexity of coping with trailing arrays. There now have to be two mechanisms instead of one, and they have to be properly matched to the message type. An increase in expected defects will ensue.

Though not as serious as the overextension disaster we previously examined, this certainly qualifies as a minor design defect.

Types 7-19: Keeping it simple again

After the spectacular efflorescence of misdesign we saw in types 6 and 8, the simplicity of type 7 "Binary acknowledge" is a relief. It adds no new field types.

More importantly: this type has a variable bit field sequence, but only because the payload is a list of MMSIs that may vary from one MMSI to four in length. This adds almost no complexity in practice as the message is a maximum of 168 bits = 21 bytes long. With a little care in initializing empty MMSI slots with the out-of-band value of zero, it can usually be treated as fixed-length.

This sort of case - a fixed bitfield sequence that may be truncated to omit unused fields at the end - will come up again. As a shorthand we will refer to these layouts as "tail-variable".

Type 9 "Standard SAR Aircraft Position Report" is also very simple; fixed-length, fixed fields, and adding no new field types (with the arguable exception of different scaling for speed over ground).

Type 10 "UTC/Date Inquiry" is a 72-bit fixed-field message that introduces no new field types. Type 11 has a layout identical to type 4 and introduces no new complexity.

Types 12 "Addressed safety-related message" and 14 "Broadcast safety-related message" are basically the common header followed by a variable-length text field, again of packed-sixbit nybbles. Maximum message length is 1008 bits = 126 bytes in both cases, so dealing with the variable length doesn't require dynamic allocation. Since any implementation will have coped with the 6-bit blunder by this point these messages add no significant additional complexity.

Type 13 "Safety-related acknowledgement" is an acknowledge for a binary broadcast message, identical in layout to type 7 and adding no additional complexity.

Types 15 "Interrogation" and 16 "Assigned mode command" are used for housekeeping functions of the AIS network and contain no navigational, ship-status or station-status information. The payload consists of MMSIs and three new field types, slot/offset/increment numbers describing timing and radio parameters. Both are tail-variable.

Type 17 "DGNSS Broadcast Binary Message" contains housekeeping information, a latitude-longitude pair, and a trailing binary blob containing differential-GPS corrections. It introduces no new field types or decoding issues. We refer the reader to [\[ITU823\]](#) for decoding the binary blob.

Type 18 "Standard Class B CS position report" and type 19: Extended Class B CS position report are subsets of the Common Navigation Block for vessels with a less sophisticated navigation and sensor suites. They introduce no new field types or decoding issues.

Type 20 "Data link management message" is another housekeeping message type similar to 15 and 16; like them, it is tail-variable and introduces no new decoding issues.

Type 21: Aide to Navigation

Complexity begins to rise again with type 21, the "Aid-to-Navigation report". This is intended to be broadcast by navigation markers such as buoys, lighthouses, and beacons.

It is largely unexceptional, introducing no new field types other than a controlled-vocabulary description of the broadcast and a boolean off-position flag, except for one curious detail. There is a packed-sixbit field available for the name of the navigation mark - but it is split in two. The first 20 packed-sixbit characters begin after bit 43; a trailing 14 characters, if required, end the message after bit 272.

This is not of a magnitude with the packed-sixbit blunder or the even worse bureaucratic snafu around the type 6 and 8 messages, but it is careless and annoying. Why not a single variable-length text field at message end? The bit of extra code required to glue those segments together is yet another avoidable failure point.

Alas, there is much worse to come.

Type 22: Channel Management

The "much worse" arrives with message type 22. It is a fixed-length housekeeping message introducing five new field types which are neither difficult to understand nor very interesting once understood. It is likely to be of interest only to those auditing or troubleshooting the AIS network itself.

But the type 22 message layout has one rather shocking design bug. The span from bit 69 to bit 138 has two different possible interpretations depending on one-bit broadcast/addressed flag, a dispatch field which is located at bit 139 **after** the variant fields.

This means that if you are stream-parsing the datagram, you don't have the information required to interpret the variant fields when you get to them. The message **must** be entirely buffered in memory to be interpreted. An entire class of elegant, lightweight analysis techniques resembling stateless LL(1) parsing in a compiler hit this wall and drop dead. The code complexity of the entire decoder, and its expected defect rate, are pushed upwards substantially.

When we discuss analyzer implementation in a later section, we will show how this irregularity in the AIS design scuppered the smallest and most lightweight AIS decoder either of us knows to exist.

Type 23: Group Assignment Command

Type 23 is similar in structure and function to type 22, a fixed-length housekeeping message introducing a few new field types concerned with AIS administrative functions. Unlike message type 22, it poses no new decoding issues.

Type 24: Static Data Report

AIS has only one more serious botch awaiting us, at least before the set of ITU1371 message types is extended again. It's in message 24, which not only has two internal dispatch fields and variant sections, but has to be assembled from two datagrams.

The dispatch fields are "part number" and vessel MMSI. Part number 0 identifies the A datagram of the pair, which will contain common header information and up to 20 packed-sixbit characters of the ship's name. Part number 1 identifies the B datagram of the pair, which may contain either ship type and dimensions or a parent vessel MMSI, depending on the format of the MMSI in the common header. (The second format is intended for use by small auxiliary craft.)

As usual, multiple dispatch fields and variant sections are defect attractors. But this design attracts whole new classes of bugs because the message spans two datagrams. What if the standard's bland assurances that they are expected to be transmitted as an adjacent pair go unfulfilled due to equipment failure, or reception as an adjacent pair is foiled by interference? What edge cases are possible, and how can we verify that a decoder will cope with them sanely? What are the potential consequences of different decoders choosing different ways to resolve edge cases?

More generally, the the split-datagram design implies that a decoder must retain parsing state between datagrams and be prepared to merge Part B information into stored Part A information. This introduces a whole level of data-management complexity that the protocol did not previously require. Expected defect rates will rise as a direct result.

There is a similar problem with the separation of RAIM and Position Accuracy in the Common Navigation Block from the actual navigation-system type information in type 5 (Static and Voyage Related Data). If there are two vessels within line-of-sight with the same MMSI (yes, the happens all the time), interpretation software may be unable to avoid mixing the position-system data for the two ships.

Types 25, 26, and 27: Anticlimax

Type 25, "Binary message, single slot", is a binary message wrapper that combines the capabilities of types 6 and 8. It differs from 6 and 8 in that an acknowledgement is not expected. It is limited to occupying a single packet-radio slot of at most 168 bits.

Type 25 introduces no new field types, but has two dispatch flags immediately after the common header that indicate whether the message is broadcast or has a destination MMSI preceding the payload, and whether or not the payload is preceded by a DAC/FID pair.

Type 25 violates the rule implied in previous message layouts that if a particular bitfield (such as DAC, FID, or destination MMSI) is present, it is always present at the same bit offset. This might

be considered a design defect, but the additional complexity imposed by it on decoders is fairly small and it is thus at worst a minor one.

Message type 26, "Binary message, single slot", is an extension of type 25 that can wrap longer binary messages. It introduces one minor new parsing difficulty; the variable-length binary payload is followed by a radio-status field. This breaks the assumption of all previous message layouts that if a message type has a variable-length payload section, it is the last field and a stream parser reaching it can consume the rest of the message. This, too, imposes additional complexity on the parsing machinery and may be considered a minor design defect.

Message 27 "Long range AIS broadcast message" is a simple subset of the Common Navigation Block intended for satellite reception. It introduces no new field types nor any new parsing difficulties.

This completes the tour of message type layouts in version 4 of the AIS specification. Next, we'll examine issue with the field inventories within those layouts.

Field-specification issues

Data fields in the AIS protocol have at least two significant attributes: length, type (signed int, unsigned int, boolean, float, controlled-vocabulary index, string, binary data). Most have two more: a scaling formula and a not-available special value. Some have other attributes that must be considered in interpretation, such as a controlled-vocabulary list or additional special values for various measurement boundaries.

Overcomplexity

Field attributes occur in a number of different combinations so large it is difficult to even estimate. This is a major source of decoder complexity and defects in itself.

But there are worse and more specific problems ranging from underspecification to poorly-chosen semantics, as we shall see next.

Underspecification

The AIS standard has serious problems with underspecification of field types and semantics. For example, the interpretation of the "Special Manoeuvre" value in Class A position messages is not specified adjacent to the message definition. No definition is supplied elsewhere in [\[ITU1371\]-4](#). In an echo of the problems with IMO message subtypes, the interpretation of "specials" is delegated to unspecified regional authorities. Thus it is impossible to evaluate whether these two bits are critical to safe operation or not, and they are very likely to slip through the cracks in software design, specification, and testing. This is a major defect.

This failure of omission is repeated a number of times throughout [\[ITU1371\]](#).

Proliferating special cases

Another class of problem comes from poorly documented special cases in field values. For example, the Search and Rescue Transmitter (SART) devices introduced in revision 4 of [\[ITU1371\]](#) create a special case that will introduce further errors. A special range of MMSI values denote devices that are for use in man overboard and vessel emergencies. If these devices accidentally have the wrong (non-SART) prefix, or if the decoding or display software does not have the proper range of SART prefixes marked, the SART device (which hopefully is attached to a person or life raft) might show up as a normal vessel thereby possibly confusing rescue personnel when seconds matter.

Complicating exceptions

In general, the formula required to extract a value in human-friendly units from an AIS message field is a simple linear transformation using a scaling factor and an offset. But there is one exception. Interpreting the Rate of Turn field in the Common Navigation Block required taking a (sign-preserving) square root and then scaling.

Exceptions like this increase the defect rate of decoders out of all proportion to the apparent ease with which they can be specified. They make it more difficult to capture the protocol in an existing specification language, and far more difficult to write a custom mini language (such as those two of our examples) that can do the job. Thus, decoder developers are reduced to fragile and error-prone hand-coding.

To add insult to injury, there is no discernible reason for this extra complexity. The field is supposed to scale to degrees per second, and could have been encoded with linear scaling like every other degree-valued field.

From a whole-systems-engineering point of view, this is a major defect.

Semantic problems

Here's a representative semantic problem: the RAIM and Position Accuracy fields occurring in several messages are essentially meaningless with today's positioning technologies and with requirements such as vessel Dynamic Positioning (DP). Reporting that positioning is better than 10m accuracy means horizontal uncertainty could be as bad as 9m, leading to the possibility of vessel and platform collisions.

9m of imprecision is certainly not enough to safely handle equipment in (for example) the oil and gas industry. A disaster comparable to the Deepwater Horizon blowout could result from a tired or stressed operator incautiously trusting an "accuracy" bit. But even ignoring disaster scenarios, meaningless fields are design failures because they cost complexity in decoders without repaying that cost in useful information. This counts as at least a minor defect.

Proliferating field variants

We have found through practice in writing decoders that the most severe problem with the AIS field inventory is the proliferation of related field types with **almost**, but not quite identical semantics. These make it difficult to avoid bugs, and difficult to detect defects after the fact.

For example, in the CNB, Course Over Ground and True Heading use different scales for a measured bearing within the same message. An incorrect heading will likely be detected quickly for software run on ships, but the possibility of updates introducing a regression at inopportune times can not be discounted.

There are similar problems across messages. As an example, there are three different pairs of bit lengths used to encode longitude/latitude pairs: one in the Common Navigation Block (and elsewhere) with precision of 10^{-4} minutes of arc, another in the IMO 289 Clearance Time To Enter Port message (and elsewhere) with precision of 10^{-3} minutes, and a third in DGNSS Broadcast Binary Message (and elsewhere) with 10^{-1} precision. Each of these types has its own, different scaling constant and not-available value.

Minor variations like these create significant risks of defects that are difficult to avoid and extremely difficult to detect if they're committed - such as mismatching a scaling constant or not-available value with a field encoded using a different minor variation of the type. Over the entire life-cycle of the protocol is a high price to pay for saving 2 to 4 bits in a few rarely-used message types.

Defective timestamps

Scattered through the AIS specification and IMO extensions are no fewer than 15 timestamp fields. Of these, only two (in message types 4 and 10) are complete date/time stamps.

This is a major design defect which creates significant problems for testing of AIS, for logging of AIS events, and for maintaining databases of AIS events. In particular, it means that for logs to be useful for replicable testing reproducing the relative timing of different logs, the logs have to embed information disambiguating their timestamps.

Different choices of how to embed this out-of-band information will lead to pointless friction and difficulties in checking the interoperability of decoder implementations.

Drawing lessons from the defects

We have so far identified a plethora of major and minor defects in the design of the AIS protocol, each one of which forces higher code complexity - and therefore higher expected defect rates - in conforming decoders. Each error implies a bit of normative advice for application-protocol designers.

1. AIS's decision to use packed-sixbit nybbles indexing a 64-bit subset of ASCII chased tiny gains in physical-layer economy for significantly higher decoder complexity. It is worth mentioning that it also forecloses the use of UTF-8 and proper internationalization of the protocol.

Lesson: Supposing you must design a packed-binary protocol that contains embedded string data, don't try to get cute with character encodings to save space. You can't squeeze out enough bits to be worth the downstream pain you will cause.

Each of the other design defects in the AIS protocol violates a regularity that was implicitly present in all datagram layouts previous to the one in which it first occurred, escalating parsing complexity for **all** message types.

1. Message types 6 and 8 broke the rule that the protocol has exactly one dispatch field and each type has a fixed (though possibly tail-variable) bitfield sequence. In doing this, they added a second extension mechanism to the protocol, and handed off control of various portions of the extension space. The resulting mess teaches several important lessons:

Lesson: Dispatch fields (those which change the logic flow of the parse) are complexity and defect attractors. The complexity cost of having multiple dispatch fields rises not additively but multiplicatively. Well-designed application protocols have just one, period.

Lesson: One protocol-extension mechanism may be just right, but two is certainly too many.

Lesson: Beware especially of extension mechanisms that encourage local options and do not enforce a common namespace in their dispatch fields. Such mechanisms are likely to turn your protocol into an unmanageable hairball in short order.

Lesson: Suffer not thy protocol design to fall into the hands of bureaucrats, for they will smother it in features.

1. Message type 21 pointlessly split a string field in two. This is a minor defect compared to the other infelicities.

Lesson: Don't do this. It adds defect-attracting moving parts to the code and complicates testing.

1. Message type 22 not only contained a second dispatch field, it located that field **after** the payload section it controlled.

Lesson: Dispatch fields should always **precede** any payload for which they modify the bitfield sequence. Otherwise you will foreclose entire classes of simple and lightweight stream-parsing techniques. (This is a perfect example of a point defect in design that imposes large complexity costs not just for the processing of that individual message type but for all types.)

1. Message type 24 has two internal dispatch fields controlling variant sections, and is split across two datagrams. In addition to the normal complexity costs of handling variant sections, this requires a conforming parser to maintain fragile state between datagrams and introduces lots of tricky edge cases.

Lesson: Never do this! The amount of statefulness that the network layers underneath your application protocol imposes on you will be a severe enough source of bugs and edge cases; deliberately fragmenting your application protocol's units of meaning to invite **more** is asking for trouble.

1. Message type 25 contains optional fields that are not at fixed offsets, adding complexity that might be considered a minor design defect.
2. Message type 26 contains a variable-length payload field that is not the last one in the message, complicating the handling of variable-length fields in stream parsers. This might be considered a minor design defect.
3. A huge proliferation of field types and variants creates excessive complexity in decoders.

Lesson: Minimize the number of field types. Good practice is for there to be just one type per natural kind; e.g. in a geolocation protocol all longitudes should be encoded with the same length, signedness, and special values. Ditto all latitudes, bearings, timestamp fields, etc.

1. The "Special Manoeuvre" field in the CNB has unspecified semantics. The (lack of) specification does not include even a handoff to a registry or document describing the use of the field, so even if "regional authorities" were to define it, decoder implementors would have no way to find the definition(s).

Lesson: Never do this! The effect of this design error is that even if some regional authority attempts to put a meaning on the field, the effort is effectively certain to fail.

1. Special-casing of MMSIs creates a bug vulnerability related to mis-recognition of SART prefixes.

Lesson: Don't make an elaborate, multi-special-case decode of a field carry information that should be passed via multiple fields with simpler decode specifications.

1. Rate of Turn in the CNB uses an unnecessarily exceptional scaling formula. And Route Information uses an exceptional mechanism for specifying the element count of a trailing array.

Lesson: Keep exception cases to a dead minimum. Remember that one tiny specification exception that's easy for a human being to process can make the protocol intractable for parser generators. A good way to think about the downstream impact is that each exception case doubles the overall cost of coding and testing, and correspondingly doubles the expected defect rate.

1. The RAIM and Position Accuracy fields occurring in several messages have become essentially meaningless and possibly dangerously misleading. They cost code complexity without conveying useful information.

Lesson: Beware of magic numbers in field definitions (like the "10 meters" in the definition of Position Accuracy) because technology can change them and likely will. Make the field say what you mean in a future-proof way (like, actually giving meters of error estimate at 95% confidence) even if that costs a few bits of space.

1. AIS timestamps are incomplete, requiring out-of-band information when keeping sentence logs.

Lesson: Never, ever define a timestamp field that isn't a complete date/time stamp in UTC. No exceptions, because you **will** come to regret every single one.

Further note: If you choose any timestamp format other than ISO8601, that is probably a design defect in itself. The advantages of a format that is readable, readily usable as a database key, and for which lexicographic sort order corresponds with time order are large.

To these defects could be added another large one that in a sense precedes all of them. At the tiny data volumes of AIS, the style of packed-bit binary protocols of which AIS is an example is a colossal error of misdirected and premature optimization, leading to rigidity and unnecessary overcomplexity. See [\[TEXTUALITY\]](#) for a more detailed argument of this position.

A tale of four decoders

Having identified the failings in the original design of the AIS protocol, and explained how these cause problems and how best to avoid them, we shall next examine the ways in which AIS's design defects hindered the development of actual AIS decoders, and how the authors coped.

The authors have written four AIS decoders in three different languages. We describe them here in historical order.

To put this list in perspective, it should be noted that AIS decoders are a rare species of software. Web searches turn up few hits, and most of those only interpret a subset of the navigational message types rather than covering the full ITU1371 standard and extensions. It is likely that the implementations we list here represent a substantial fraction of all the decoders in existence that are at or near full conformance.

noadata

Noadata was designed primarily as a research tool to explore methods for working with AIS messages and the data contained within the many message types. Development began in early 2007. Schwehr chose to drive his decoder from a protocol-description minilanguage. This architecture was aimed at easy generation of language-native parsers and other tools, including SQL schema generators and translation tools to container formats such as GeoJSON and YAML. A minilanguage-driven parser would also greatly reduce the effort required to support new ITU-standard messages and experimental messages.

This original architectural vision for noadata disintegrated with the horrible inevitability of a Greek tragedy under the weight of AIS's specifications. We will describe the process in some detail here because it shows exactly what the downstream costs of intrinsic protocol complexity look like in actual practice.

The first major design decision was what protocol-description language to use. Schwehr considered but rejected ASN.1 and bdec, finding them cumbersome and a poor fit to AIS's extremely bit-oriented layout. Schwehr chose to design a specialized minilanguage expressed as a custom XML application. As the AIS message standard is written in MS Word and Excel as

free form English text, the first major task was to hand-translate the content of the standard into a set of XML message-layout definitions.

An initial barrier to actually doing anything with the XML message definitions was that XML parser generators also proved cumbersome and poorly suited to the task. Writing a complete XML schema in any of the three major schema languages - [\[RelaxNG\]](#), [\[Schematron\]](#), XML Schema Definition [\[XSD\]](#) - would have consumed more time than available to a single researcher who had no experience in XML schemas. Even supposing the commitment to do so could have been sustained, DTDs offer so little leverage as to be pointless for checking a document format as heavily structured as the task required.

Early versions of noadata therefore used lxml, an element-tree XML API written in Python, to directly walk the XML tree of message definitions as noadata decoded each incoming AIS message. But while walking the XML tree during the actual parsing is compact in terms of number of lines of code, it is extremely slow. Later versions of noadata addressed the performance problem by splitting the parser into two stages: a code generator read the XML and emitted static Python code that could decode and encode AIS messages.

The code-generation process added its own layer of complexity. The generator uses the FIX templating language, bringing the number of formalisms being juggled to three (Python, XML, FIX) and causing the process of modifying the Python output to be more annoying than it should have been.

At each stage in the process, the intrinsic complexity and irregularity of AIS rendered inadequate the tools for high-level description of the protocol and forced Schwehr into using progressively more ad-hoc and complex implementation methods. Not only did the XML message definitions fail to capture AIS's structure, it gradually became apparent that no minilanguage with a description complexity substantially less than that of a hand-coded parser could do so.

As the prospect of an XML definition language with the full capability to handle all the odd conditional cases receded, Schwehr started to fork copies of the generated Python to add support for conditional data based on values in fields and inspecting the lengths of messages when necessary. This, of course, subverted the original architecture.

By the time Raymond wrote a critique of the code in 2009 for Schwehr it was already clear that the noadata codebase was out of control. When time came to implement the IMO289 environment and zone messages in late 2010, the XML definition system completely collapsed.

Near the beginning of the development effort, Schwehr and Alexander [\[IHO2007\]](#) had proposed an initial XML definition language in an attempt to engage the AIS standards community. While personal feedback from individual members of that community was positive, the standards community never formally engaged it, criticized it, or helped develop it. That lack of interest put the seal on the collapse of the architecture, removing the motivation for any rescue effort.

All of the problems with noadata that we have described so far were entailed by the design of AIS. It is worth noting one other that is perhaps more a function of implementation: despite a good deal of effort put into time optimization, the code is too slow. As of early 2011 it cannot handle real time data from the NAIS network feed.

A large portion of this speed issue comes from using the pure Python BitVector library [\[BitVector\]](#). While this library makes working with bits very easy, it is not designed for speed. In 2009 Raymond reimplemented the BitVector interface using Python's array type and achieved substantial performance gains, but it still proved a bottleneck in his Python decoder, suggesting that we'll need a few more cycles of Moore's Law before any an interpreted language is up to meeting the throughput requirements for this task.

This performance problem could be addressed by creating a cBitVector implementation that presents the same interface, but knows how to efficiently create sub-slices of bit vectors using copy-on-write storage management.

Despite all these systemic problems, noadata has proven successful as a research tool: generating test cases for AIS libraries, creating initial SQL database definitions, demonstrating the potential for XML definitions to produce more friendly HTML documentation with an XSLT transformation, demonstration of how a registry could enable all software vendors to handle an explosion of AIS message types, exploring the concept of automatic testing of new message proposals, and so forth.

The noadata suite was also extremely useful in the process of validating the next two decoders we shall examine.

Noadata also suggested strategies for optimization of AIS data processing based on the task at hand. For example, tracking ships in real time might only require processing a small portion of the class A and B messages. If the external time stamp can be trusted (not always the case in NAIS), then there may be no need to look at the timing data for quick-look visualizations. Deep statistical analysis of AIS data requires looking at most or all of the data on the channel to understand which data can be used and what problems must be addressed in the analysis.

GPSD

GPSD is an open-source monitoring daemon for GPSes and other kinematic/geodetic sensors. It turns the raw take from sensors into JSON messages on a well-known TCP/IP port, insulating client applications from the grubby details of vendor protocols and hardware quirks. Besides being a stock piece of infrastructure on Linux and *BSD laptops running location-aware applications, it is extremely widely deployed in embedded systems including cellphones, scientific telemetry packages, and autonomous robotic vehicles including a DARPA Grand Challenge entry and the Woods Hole Institute's deep-diving Nereus submarine.

One of us (Raymond) developed an interest in AIS through GPSD, for which he is the project lead. He began work on supporting sensors reporting AIVDM/AIVDO in GPSD in 2009, and compiled [\[RAYMOND1\]](#) as part of his effort to pull together enough information to do a proper implementation. Schwehr contributed advice and test loads, and the authors became acquainted through cooperating to improve this software.

The GPSD AIVDM driver is implemented in approximately a thousand lines of C. At time of writing it has tested support for AIS message types 1-15, 18-21, and 24. It has untested support for types 16-17, 22-23, 25-27 and most of the IMO extension messages, many of which have

not yet been observed in the wild. Conformance was tested by comparison with reports from Schwehr's noadata driver operating on samples from [\[AISHUB\]](#) and elsewhere.

Most of the driver is hand-coded, because at the time it was constructed the author believed AIS was too irregular for an attempt at driver code generation based on a protocol specification to work. This belief was based partly on experience with Schwehr's noadata code.

However, in early 2011 Raymond built a small suite of code generators that take any message-layout table from [\[RAYMOND1\]](#) as input and generate snippets of C and Python code as output. These snippets include a C structure declaration for the unpacked message data, and driver code to extract the bits into the structure. While these code generators cannot produce all of the the high-level logic required for the AIVDM driver, they do reliably automate the most fiddly and defect-prone parts of datagram analysis.

The design problems of AIS have not prevented this driver from parsing the full range of message types, mainly because hand-coded C allows an approach of using brute force to overpower those problems. The resulting code is hardly elegant, but it works for production uses.

The intrinsic complexity of AIS has taken its toll, however. GPSD reports AIS sentences as equivalent JSON objects. GPSD ships a library for C client applications that unmarshals the JSON into C structures, using a custom JSON parser that uses only static-extent storage. The JSON generated by certain IMO extension messages (notably Area Notice and Environmental) is so complex that the library JSON parser breaks on it and probably cannot be extended to work without using dynamic storage.

As of May 2011 the GPSD AIVDM driver is the most capable AIS decoder available in open source. Despite the driver's problems and limitations, field experience with other implementations and the known difficulty of conforming with the murkier corners of the AIS standards cause the authors to strongly suspect that the GPSD AIVDM driver is the most capable AIS decoder available anywhere. The authors are not pleased or reassured by this evaluation, considering it mainly a reflection of the shambolic state of the AIS standards.

[ais.py](#)

[ais.py](#) is an undistributed developer tool in the repository of the GPSD project. Raymond wrote it as a check on the project's C decoder, using as different an implementation strategy as he could imagine and attempting to avoid noadata's problems. It is not intended as a production tool.

[ais.py](#) is approximately a thousand lines of Python code, which includes extensive report-generation features as well as the datagram analysis. Most of the code consists of lists of declarations in a tiny domain-specific language adapted for describing the layout of AIS datagrams; these are interpreted by 250 lines of a relatively simple execution loop.

While this approach is far more elegant than ad-hoc C code and in many ways more successful than noadata, it runs headlong into AIS's design errors. The execution loop is essentially a recursive stream parser and cannot handle the post-positioned dispatch field in message type 22. It cannot merge the A and B parts of message type 24. It cannot handle the embedded

variable-length string field in message type 26 (though this could be fixed relatively easily by extending the mini language). It handles the split string field in message type 21 only via a rather embarrassing kluge. And it does not handle the IMO specials of type 6 and 8 at all.

As with noadata, ais.py shows that in a collision between declarative specification and the ugly realities of AIS, declarative specification does not fare very well.

ais.py also has a performance problem unrelated to AIS complexity; on PC hardware generally available at present (May 2011) it is not fast enough to handle a real-time stream from AISHub. This is an issue with the performance of bit-vector operations under Python, and would probably be replicated in any other scripting language.

libais

Libais is a C++ hand coded parser for AIS messages. It was written to replace noadata for the ERMA / GeoPlatform response to Deepwater Horizon [[Schwehr2011](#)] when noadata was not able to keep up with the real time volume of AIS traffic from 5000 vessels in the NAIS network. The design is a hand-written, very simple object-oriented class tree using inheritance. A CPython interface is provided that returns a dictionary for each AIS message.

Drawing lessons from the implementations

Lesson: Do a reference implementation **before** you publish an application protocol as a standard.

No application protocol with as many design problems as AIS has would have made it out of committee if a reference decoder had been in development in parallel with the specification; implementation problems would have thrown them into sharp relief.

The IETF (Internet Engineering Task Force) has a custom of not allowing a network protocol design to be published as a proposed standard until it has at least two conforming implementations. This would be a good practice for everyone else to emulate.

We would go even further and say that as a best practice, the reference implementation should be open source. In this way, third parties can see exactly what degree of complexity is required to implement the standard, exerting a valuable pressure towards simplicity.

Lesson: Design your protocol with a small and consistent set of idioms

Both of the authors had plans to generate an AIS decoder with at least conditionally provable correctness from a declarative specification. Both efforts (the noadata decoder and ais.py) failed because AIS is just plain too irregular to be captured this way.

We recommend that application-protocol designers should, as a routine part of their process, render the design as a specification in [[ASN.1](#)] or [[BDEC](#)]. If this process is painful and complex, writing a decoder will also be painful and complex, and the design should be considered broken until that is fixed.

Lesson: Ship your standard with test pairs.

Both authors find that, even as mis-designed as parts of AIS are, the single most frustrating thing about writing AIS decoders is not any one of those design problems or even all of them together. The worst problem is our inability to verify that the code we write is correct.

This problem could be quite easily be fixed by attaching to the standard a set of test pairs - that is, an example binary datagram in each of every possible variation of message shape together with a textual, human-readable decode of that datagram.

Shipping test pairs with a standard has particular importance in application protocols for life-critical software, where mistakes can easily kill. But it's good practice everywhere. The combination of official test pairs with an open-source reference implementation is the most effective means we know of to ensure that a standard is implemented correctly and completely.

Lesson: Closed, paywalled standards endanger lives.

While writing our decoders we had occasion to evaluate about a dozen others. For some, such as [\[GNU-AIS\]](#), we could read source code; for others, we could only see sample results and read documentation.

The completeness and correctness of these implementations was generally poor. Most could handle only a small subset of the AIS messages - typically 1, 2, 3, and 5. We found bugs on even the most superficial examination. It quickly became evident that these limitations were a result of the actual standards being relatively expensive and inaccessible; implementers had been reduced to trying to reverse-engineer the standard from information that had leaked out about it, and not uncommonly made errors in doing so.

While that situation was alleviated by the publication of [\[RAYMOND1\]](#) and later by an ITU policy change that made [\[ITU1371\]](#) available as a free download, those poor implementations are still with us. Someday, incautious use of one of them might well kill somebody.

The lesson is clear. Making a standard expensive to get damages the quality of attempted implementations. This is flat-out unacceptable when the standard is life-critical. Even when it is not, we can expect the costs and damages imposed by paywalling to greatly exceed the maximum revenue anyone can ever expect to collect from it; the economist's concept of "deadweight loss" applies with particular force here.

Ways forward for AIS

The AIS protocol's design problems will not be easily solved. Implementations are widely dispersed and often difficult to access for firmware upgrades, so the deployment problem is significant. Some major defects, such as the handling of string data, are too deeply embedded to be removed. But there are steps that could be taken to improve the quality of decoders and prevent further proliferation of dangerous complexity.

A vital first step would be publication of a definitive set of test pairs in conjunction with the standard and any future extensions. The ITU should also mandate that all extensions by

jurisdiction authorities also publish complete sets of test pairs. With such a conformance suite to test against, quality and breadth of conformance in AIS decoders would improve dramatically and rapidly.

The single point defect with the largest ripple effect on complexity of implementation is probably the post-positioned dispatch field in message type 22. Deprecating this message and replacing it with a better-structured one would eventually enable a significant reduction in decoder complexity.

Most of the rest of our guidance for designers of future AIS messages should be obvious from the design rules we've pointed out. Dispatch fields are complexity poison, so keep them to a bare minimum; don't split string fields; avoid fields with variable offsets; don't split message layouts across multiple datagrams.

Again, life-critical systems concentrate the mind wonderfully. We cannot stress strongly enough that, in an application domain like AIS's, bad protocol-design decisions are not merely annoying but, because of the way they feed through into increased code complexity and defect rates, actually dangerous.

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- [CATB] [The Cathedral and the Bazaar](#)
- [IEC-PAS] IEC-PAS 61162-100, "Maritime navigation and radiocommunication equipment and systems" The ASCII armoring is described on page 26 of Annex C, Table C-1.
- [AISHUB] [AIS Hub, the AIS data sharing center](#)
- [TEXTUALITY] [The Importance of Being Textual](#).
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